

Compostable and recycled plastics do not improve environmental chemical safety compared to conventional single-use polyethylene

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Comprehensive analysis of 130 additives, monomers, and 23 metals in plastic bags.
- Compostable bags contain more chemical additives than conventional PE bags.
- Higher orthophthalate and OPFR concentrations found in compostable bags vs. PE.
- Compostable bag leachates exhibit moderate toxicity to marine plankton.
- Recycled PE bags have higher Cu and Zn levels than single-use PE and compostable bags.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Due to recent regulations encouraging the reduction of single-use plastic waste, compostable plastics are replacing polyethylene (PE) for applications in the form of thin films. Seven commercial brands of compostable bags and three brands of PE bags (conventional, oxodegradable and recycled), as well as their corresponding resins, were assessed in terms of major components of the polymeric matrix, qualitative and quantitative composition in additives of bags and their leachates, and ecotoxicological effects on test species representative of the main marine taxa, namely microalgae, copepods, sea-urchin embryos, bivalves and fish. Polybutylene-adipate-terephthalate (PBAT), an oil-based polymer, was the main component of all compostable bags analysed, and most of them also included in their composition polylactic-acid (PLA) and starch. Compostable bags showed a higher number of chemical additives than conventional PE bags, and generally higher concentrations of phthalate plasticizers and organophosphate flame retardants. This includes chemicals registered in the EU as exhibiting acute and chronic aquatic toxicity levels 1 and 2. Following standard procedures for plastic leachates, no effects of any product were found on microalgae and fish larva, but bioplastics consistently showed a higher short term aquatic toxicity to marine invertebrates compared to PE items. None of the toxicity levels found

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though support concerning effects at environmentally relevant plastic densities. Remarkably higher levels of some metals were found in recycled PE compared to first-use conventional PE bags. In conclusion, based on these findings, compostable bags cannot be considered chemically or ecotoxicologically safer products than PE bags.

1. Introduction

The high functionality and relatively low cost of plastic made this material increasingly ubiquitous in everyday life. Last year, global plastic production exceeded by first time the 400 MT (Plastics Europe, 2023). Conventional plastics such as polyethylene (PE), either made from oil or biomass, are not amenable to biodegradation in the natural environment, and thus show undesirable environmental persistence. As a consequence of littering and inadequate waste disposal, an estimated 11 % of global plastic production ends up in aquatic ecosystems (Borrelle et al., 2020), and plastic litter is an aesthetical nuisance in coastal and oceanic habitats (Galvani et al., 2019), posing a threat of smothering and obstruction of the digestive system to marine wildlife (Kühn et al., 2015).

Low-density PE bags, along with packaging film and food containers, are the most commonly produced plastic consumer products, and these materials are the most abundant marine litter items in the coast (UNEP, 2021) and in the seafloor (Maes et al., 2018). In an attempt to solve the issue of accumulation of plastic litter in the environment, potentially biodegradable plastics in compliance with multiple certification schemes and labels have been introduced in the market (Emadian et al., 2017; Krzan et al., 2006). In Europe, the EN-13432 (CEN, 2000) sets the standards for packaging to be considered as compostable in industrial composting facilities, whereas EN-17427 (CEN, 2022) is normally used to test biodegradability in home composting installations. In the US, the ASTM D6400-04 is used to certify plastics suitable for municipal and industrial aerobic composting facilities. Currently, many carrier bags and trash sacs in the market meet these standards, and they are presented as amenable to biodegradation at least under certain environmental conditions, and thus a convenient replacement for conventional PE bags. In these novel materials, the C—C bond of the PE chains is replaced by C—O ester bonds. Polybutylene-adipate-terephthalate (PBAT), an oil-based aliphatic-aromatic polyester made from terephthalic acid, adipic acid and 1,4-butanediol, was first introduced in the market under the commercial trademark Ecoflex. PBAT presents a remarkable performance in terms of processability (Owonubi et al., 2018), and it is currently the main component of compostable plastic bags (Tullo, 2021), although bio-based polymers and plasticizing additives are frequently included as major components in the final product.

Whereas reduced environmental persistence can be a strong point of these novel materials, they do not necessarily solve potential toxicity of their chemical components. Zimmermann et al. (2020) found that extracts from cellulose- and starch-based materials generally triggered a strong *in vitro* toxicity as a consequence of the complex mixture of unknown chemicals that they contained. Processability and technical performance, in terms of mechanical properties of the final product, limit the utility of potentially biodegradable polymers (Tang et al., 2012), and specific additives designed to overcome this limitation are added in quantities around 10–15 % in weight (Wacker, 2023). Biodegradable plastics may require also special functional additives. This is the case of alginate-based films, which despite outstanding biodegradability suffer from poor antimicrobial and UV-barrier properties and require light protectants such as ZnO nanoparticles (Abdel Aziz and Salama, 2022). Moreover, the commercialization of the known as oxo-biodegradable plastics, currently restricted, aggravated this problem. Apart from stabilizers, their composition includes pro-degradant agents, which are activated upon UV radiation or heat exposure and generate smaller plastic particles, not necessarily biodegradable and potentially toxic (Schiavo et al., 2020).

Even if compostable materials would carry same additives as

conventional plastics, due to their biodegradability, the potential for their environmental release is necessarily higher (Tao et al., 2024). In fact, persistence and toxicity may be inversely related. The release of bioactive degradation products, derived from both the polymer chain and the additives, is inherent to biodegradability and will occur during the environmental degradation of these novel materials (Gewert et al., 2018). Either these degradation products themselves (Klein et al., 2021a), or the microbial flora promoted during biodegradation might have a negative impact on sensitive live stages of marine organisms, such as invertebrate larvae making part of the plankton.

In addition, about half of the plastic materials are intended for single use. In order to reduce the volume of plastic waste, multiple regulatory initiatives such as those in Europe (European Directive EU 2019/904), Japan (Government of Japan, 2022) and some US States (Mo, 2020) are progressively restricting single use items and promoting recycled materials. In the EU these regulations impose the target of 77 % and 90 % recycling for certain single-use plastic items by 2025 and 2029 respectively. According to current estimations, the global market of recycled polyethylene will grow from 11.3 billion US dollars (USD) in 2020 to 24.4 billion USD in 2028 as a consequence of the adoption of those regulations (Globe Newswire, 2023).

The aim of this study was to assess the chemical composition, in terms of both major components of the polymer matrix and chemical additives, and marine ecotoxicological profile of commercial plastics with different levels of biodegradability. With that aim, certified compostable plastic bags –including both home-compostable and industrial-compostable– were compared with conventional, oxodegradable and recycled polyethylene bags. The study included, on the one hand novel and up-to-date analytical techniques to unravel the complex composition of plastic items, and on the other hand, ecotoxicological bioassays with standard test species representative of marine ecosystems, from primary producers (microalgae) to fish. Early life stages and sublethal endpoints are used in this ecotoxicological assessment in order to increase sensitivity and promote early warning signals of potential ecological impact of the tested materials.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Test materials

Test materials were purchased online after a comprehensive search for suppliers of plastic resins, carrier bags and trash sacs exhibiting some labelling or certification related to compostability or degradability. Most potentially biodegradable materials found exhibited the OK-compost labels based on EN-13432. The final list of materials tested is shown in Table 1. Upon receipt, the identity of the polymers was verified using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and thermo-desorption pyrolysis gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (TD/Py-GC–MS) as described below. For compostable bags, the presence of starch was additionally ascertained by the iodine test. The reagent used in iodine test is Lugol's iodine, an aqueous solution of elemental iodine and potassium iodide. In the presence of starch, a change in color of the solution is observed, from brown/yellow to blue/purple (Tiwari, 2015).

2.2. Chemical analyses

2.2.1. Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

A 400 FT-IR PerkinElmer Spectrometer (4000–650 cm^{-1} , 4 cm^{-1} nominal resolution, Beer-nNorton strong apodization, 50 scans per spectrum, background-, depth-penetration- and baseline-correction)

Table 1

Characteristics of the tested materials. LDPE: low density polyethylene; PE: polyethylene; PBAT: polybutylene-adipate-terephthalate; PLA: poly-lactic acid; EVA: ethylene-vinyl-acetate. The base polymer and other major components were identified by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy and pyrolysis gas chromatography mass spectrometry analysis.

ID	Description	Source	Polymer base and other major components	Labels
PE materials				
IDARP	LDPE resin pellets	AIMPLAS, Spain	PE	None
ID017	Conventional PE carrier bag (10 L)	Pampols, Spain	PE	None
ID018	Oxodegradable carrier bag (10 L)	MSDS-Solutionz, UK	PE, CaCO ₃	100 % degradable
ID046	Recycled trash sack (30 L)	Relevo, Spain	PE, EVA, CaCO ₃	Recycled
Compostable materials				
ID068	PBAT resin pellets (Ecoflex 1200)	AIMPLAS, Spain	PBAT	None
ID016	Home compostable bag (6 L)	GreenMaker, China	PBAT, starch	TUV Austria OK compost home, EN13432, compostable 7P2277 (seedling)
ID045	Home compostable trash sack (30 L)	BioBag, US	PBAT, starch	TUV Austria OK compost home, ASTM D6400, EN13432, compostable 7P2045 (seedling)
ID015	Industrial compostable carrier bag (6 L)	EcoPack, Spain	PBAT, PLA, starch	TUV Austria OK compost Industrial, EN13432
ID069	Industrial compostable trash sack (6 L)	Greener Walker, China	PBAT, starch	100 % biodegradable, BPI Compostable industrial facilities, EN 13432, 7P1069 (seedling)
ID070	Industrial-compostable can liner (50 L)	Heritage, US	PBAT, talc, other polyesters	BPI compostable industrial facilities, ASTM D6400-99
ID072	Compostable trash sack (10 L)	Saplex, Spain	PBAT, starch, other polyesters	100 % compostable
ID073	Industrial-compostable trash sack (30 L)	Vileda, Germany	PBAT, starch, other polyesters	100 % bio, TUV Austria OK compost industrial, EN1342

equipped with a horizontal one-bounce attenuated total reflectance (ATR) diamond crystal (Miracle ATR, Pike) was employed throughout. Commercial databases and an ad-hoc custom library built by UDC were used for the identification and comparison of polymer particles.

2.2.2. Thermo-desorption pyrolysis gas chromatography mass spectrometry (TD/Py-GC-MS)

TD/Py-GC-MS qualitative analysis was performed with a micro-furnace pyrolyzer EGA/Py-3030D equipped with an autosampler (both Frontier Labs, Japan) attached to an Agilent gas chromatograph with a DB-5MS column coupled to an Agilent MSD mass spectrometer. The polymer identification was performed comparing the average mass spectrum of the analysed sample with a polymer library using F-search

software.

The analysis was performed in double-shot mode, i.e. first a thermo-desorption (TD) of the sample, which allows the identification by TD-GC-MS of the most volatile additives and other organic contaminants, followed by pyrolysis (Py), which allows the identification of the constituent polymer(s) of the sample and the less volatile additives by Py-GC-MS. The thermo-desorption conditions in the pyrolyzer were 40 °C increasing at 40 °C/min up to 310 °C (1 min). Pyrolysis conditions were 600 °C for 0.5 min.

2.2.3. In-tube extraction dynamic headspace sampling coupled to gas chromatography mass spectrometry (ITEX-DHS-GC-MS/MS)

Quantitative analysis of 51 target organic additives used as plasticizers, antioxidants, light-stabilizers, flame retardants, and preservatives (Tables S1 and S2) in polymeric materials was performed by ITEX-DHS using the ITEX tool of a CombiPAL CTC PAL 3 RTC (CTC Analytics AG, Switzerland) combined with gas chromatography (HP-5 MS UI 30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 µm GC column) and mass spectrometry determination (MS/MS, QQQ) (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, USA). In brief, 0.5 g of sample were heated at 200 °C, then extracted using a Tenax TA 80/100 mesh ITEX trap (CTC Analytics) and then desorbed in the GC injector (Concha-Graña et al., 2024). In addition, quantitative analysis of 50 volatile organic compounds in bag samples and leachates was carried out by Research Support Services from *Universidade da Coruña* (UDC) using also ITEX-DHS-GC-MS/MS with a Teknokroma Sapiens 624 MS 30 m × 0.25 mm × 1.4 µm column (Teknokroma Analitica S.A., Barcelona, Spain), extracting 2 g of sample at 60 °C ITEX temperature.

2.2.4. Arrow solid-phase microextraction coupled to gas chromatography mass spectrometry (SPME-Arrow-GC-MS/MS)

In selected leachate samples of home-compostable, industrial-compostable and conventional and recycled PE bags, quantitative analysis of 51 target organic additives was performed by Arrow Solid-Phase Microextraction with gas chromatography and tandem mass spectrometry determination (SPME-Arrow-GC-MS/MS), using the CombiPAL CTC tool for SPME-Arrow, and the same equipment described in the previous section (Section 2.2.3). In brief, 20 mL of leachate were extracted at 40 °C during 90 min using a PDMS/DVB 120 µm fibre (Concha-Graña et al., 2022).

2.2.5. Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)

Analysis of metal content in bags and their leachates was carried out by Research Support Services from UDC, using microwave-assisted extraction and high resolution ICP-MS determination (Element XR, Thermo-Finishing). Briefly, 0.1 g of sample ($n = 3$) was digested in a microwave oven with HNO₃, HCl and H₂O₂, and analysed by ICP-MS. For the analysis of metals from leachates, the samples were filtered and acidified with HNO₃ to achieve pH < 2 and analysed by ICP-MS.

2.3. Leachate preparation and toxicity testing

Leachates were prepared according to standard procedures specifically developed for plastics (Almeda et al., 2023). Materials mixed with dry ice were ground by using a RETSCH ZM200 Ultra Centrifuge Mill and sieved through a ISO-certified 250-µm metallic mesh. The resulting powder was transferred into 50-mL glass bottles filled with artificial seawater (ASW) (Lorenzo et al., 2002) at a proportion of 1 or 10 g/L. The bottles were incubated for 24 h at 20 °C in darkness, using an overhead rotator (GFL 3040) at 1 rpm to keep the plastic particles in suspension. After incubation, the leachates were filtrated by glass fibre filters (Whatman GF/F, nominal pore size 0.7 µm), and frozen in glass vials when intended for chemical analyses or otherwise tested with the marine toxicity bioassays. With that aim, geometric serial dilutions were made in ASW (x1 or undiluted, x1/3, x1/10, and x1/30 unless otherwise stated). All leachates were tested within a few hours after preparation,

and controls of untreated and filtered ASW were run along with all trials. Leachate toxicity was assayed using the microalga *Tisochrysis lutea*, nauplius larvae of *Acartia* sp. copepods, and embryos of the echinoderm *Paracentrotus lividus*, the bivalve *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and the fish *Cyprinodon variegatus*. All bioassays were conducted according to internationally accepted standard methods described in detail in pages 2 and 3 of the Supplementary material.

2.4. Effect of bacteria on toxicity

A comparative SET including sterile and standard leachates was also conducted, with a view to assessing the microbial influence in the biological response recorded, length increase, given the high sensitivity of the sea urchin larvae. In this case, the test was carried out using the home-compostable bag ID016 (see Table 1), selected on the basis of its high biodegradability in laboratory and mesocosm conditions (Beiras and López-Ibáñez, 2023; Quade et al., 2022). Leachates obtained with the standard method using Whatman GF/F filters (see Section 2.3), were tested in parallel with sterile leachates. In order to obtain the latter, sterile 0.22- μm filters (Fisher Scientific, Sweden), the size commonly used in aquaculture hatcheries to obtain sterile culture media, were used, and all lab-ware was previously sterilized in an autoclave at 121 °C for 20 min. In addition, at $t = 0$ (concurring with the start of the SET experiment) both types of leachates were plated in marine agar and incubated at 20 °C in dark conditions along with the SET vials for 48 h. Colony-forming units (CFU) per mL were counted after the incubation period.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Polymer identification by FTIR spectroscopy

The FTIR spectra of samples ID017, 018 and 046 identified these bags as composed by PE with a correlation percentage of 97 %, 95 % and 97 % respectively using a commercial library, and 99 % in the three cases using our custom library (Figs. 1A, B; S1). The FTIR spectra of samples ID015, 016, 045, 069, 070, 072 and 073 were not identified by the commercial library. However, the custom library built by UDC identified these bags as composed of PBAT, with correlation percentages of 92, 86, 94, 87, 93, 90 and 88 % respectively compared with ad hoc measurements of pristine PBAT (Figs. 1C, D; S1). The bands of the infrared spectra for the seven bags corresponded closely with those of the pristine PBAT spectrum. A detailed explanation of these FTIR spectra is included in the supplementary material.

3.2. Chemical characterization by TD/Py-GC-MS

3.2.1. Polymer identification by Py-GC-MS

In addition to FTIR, the identification of the type of polymer in the samples has been verified by Py-GC-MS. The mass spectra of the pyrolyzed samples ID017, 018 and 046 are the same, and the three of them were identified according to the Fsearch library as PE (99 % correlation match) (Figs. S3A and S4). In contrast, samples ID015, 016, 045, 069, 070, 072 and 073 (Figs. S3B, 2, and S4) were identified by their pyrograms as a Polyester with adipic and terephthalic acids (C1-C40), with correlation coefficients of 85, 90, 86, 86, 78, 84 and 82 % respectively.

The presence of PBAT as main polymeric matrix in all compostable bags studied is further supported by the identification in their pyrograms of several compounds likely derived from PBAT building blocks, such as adipates with different butyl groups, and esters of phthalic and terephthalic acids (Fig. S5). In fact, the combined Py-TD-GC-MS analysis (Table 2) identifies a cluster of chemicals common to PBAT resin and all compostable bags, structurally related with the PBAT building blocks, namely 1,3-butadiene, adipate esters with butyl groups (monobut 3-enyl adipate, dibut 3-enyl adipate, but 3enyl 4-pentanoyloxy butyl adipate), cyclopentanone, 2-cyclopentenone, 3-butenylpentanoate, biphenyl and tetrahydrofuran. Tetrahydrofuran and 1,3-butadiene are pyrolytic products of the PBAT unit 1,4-butanediol, whereas cyclopentanone is produced by the pyrolysis of adipate (Sato et al., 2001). Another chemical identified in compostable bags related to PBAT is 1,6-Dioxacyclododecane-7,12-dione, a by-product in the synthesis of PBAT produced by reaction of adipic acid and butanediol (Nifant'ev et al., 2022).

In agreement with the FTIR findings, a characteristic marker of PLA, 3,6-Dimethyl-1,4-dioxane-2,5-dione (DL form) is identified by Py-GC-MS in bags ID015 (Fig. 2), 070, 072 and 073. PLA/PBAT blends are often combined to overcome each other limitations, such as high production costs, sensitivity to UV and low tensile strength of PBAT, and brittleness, low flexibility, low toughness and low thermal stability during processing of PLA (De Falco et al., 2023). Impact strength of PLA/PBAT blends dramatically increased from 2.6 for neat PLA to 4.4 kJ/m² for a 80:20 PLA/PBAT blend (Jiang, 2006).

3.2.2. Qualitative analysis of plastics composition by TD/Py-GC-MS

The TD/Py-GC-MS analysis conducted in double-shot mode allowed, in addition to polymer identification, a qualitative analysis of plastic additives, monomers, and other volatile compounds present in the samples, and their pyrolysis derivatives. The chemical composition of PE vs compostable bags was remarkably different (Table 2). Only 16 chemicals were detected in both kinds of bags, whereas 64 chemicals

Fig. 1. ATR-FTIR spectra of samples A) ID018, B) ID046 (both identified as PE with CaCo3 as filler), and compostable bags: C) ID045 with PBAT resin spectrum superposed, and D) ID070 with PBAT resin spectrum superposed.

Fig. 2. Pyrogram section of ID015 sample showing the chromatographic peak and MS spectrum of the compound 3,6-Dimethyl-1,4-dioxane-2,5-dion (DL form), a PLA marker.

were found in compostable bags only, and >100 (mostly oligomers) in PE bags only. Whereas chemicals exclusive of compostable bags are mainly functional additives, the compounds exclusively identified in the PE are, with a single exception (Tributylene glycol dibutyl ether), residual oligomers such as n-alkane, α -alkene and α,ω -alkanediene triplets, typical of PE pyrograms (González-Pérez et al., 2015). When those linear aliphatic hydrocarbons along with some methylated forms also likely derived from the polyethylene chains were excluded, PE bags showed only 11 exclusive chemicals not present in compostable bags: 6 fatty aldehydes from 8 to 18C, 1-octadecanol, cyclopentene, methylcyclopentane, cyclohexene, and tributylene glycol dibutyl ether, the latter exclusive of the oxodegradable bag (ID018). The compounds found in the thermo-desorption of the three polyethylene samples are very similar, with some exceptions such as the selective presence of aliphatic aldehydes. Compounds of that type (octanal, nonanal, dodecanal, tridecanal, hexadecanal) are found in samples ID018 (oxodegradable bag) and ID046 (recycled bag), and are not present in sample ID017 (conventional PE) in which only octadecanal is detected.

Typical plasticizers such as orthophthalates were identified with high percentage of correlation only in compostable bags and in the PBAT resin. Most adipates, also used as plasticizers, were exclusive of the compostable bags, but as discussed above they could also be derived from PBAT, since adipic acid is one of the building blocks of this polymer. Only Dibut-3-enyl-butane-1,4-diyl diadipate was also identified in the conventional PE bag (ID017). The common coupling agent Hexamethylene diisocyanate was exclusively identified in the PBAT resin.

Benzoic acid and two benzoates (but 3-enyl benzoate, 2hydroxyethyl benzoate) were common to PBAT resin and all compostable bags but were absent from all PE bags. Benzoic acid is a food-compatible preservative used in PBAT materials to confer them antimicrobial properties (Wangprasertkul et al., 2021). In contrast, butane-1,4-diyl dibenzoate was present in all compostable materials but also in conventional PE (ID017), although the % correlation in this material was rather low (74 %).

Glycerol was identified in several compostable bags but not in the PBAT resin, which suggests its use as additive. Glycerol can be added to thermoplastic starch and other biopolymers as a plasticizer (Harussani et al., 2021), but it is used in PBAT also as a branching agent to increase the mechanical performance of the material and produce thinner films (Nifant'ev et al., 2022). Compounds such as methylglyoxal or levoglucosan, which can derive from glycerol or from polysaccharide structures such as starch or cellulose, are also found in the pyrograms of many compostable bags, but not in that of pristine PBAT. Novamont developed

starch-based biodegradable materials under the Mater-Bi trademark. This material combines thermoplastic starch with synthetic polymers. In the literature, Mater-Bi mulch films are reported either as blends of starch/polycaprolactone, or of starch/PBAT (De Falco et al., 2023). The compound 3,6-dimethyl-1,4-dioxane-2,5-dion (lactide), used as precursor for the polymerization of PLA, is also found in the thermo-desorption chromatogram of samples ID015 and 070, supporting again the presence of PLA in those materials.

Other chemicals found in compostable bags but not in the PBAT resin include UV-filter benzophenone, extrusion processing aid erucamide, and other additives such as methyl acrylate, styrene and hexanoic acid. Fatty acids and amides are used as processing aids in plastics. Stearic acid, hexadecanamide and erucamide were exclusive of compostable bags, whereas palmitic and oleic acids and oleamide were present in both kinds of bags. The addition of fatty acids to biopolymer films composed of lipophilic starch and gelatine improves some of their properties, such as thickness, elongation and opacity (Fakhouri et al., 2009).

Other compounds common to both types of bags identified in the chromatograms are 1,6,13,18-tetraoxacyclotetracosane-7,12,19,24-tetraone, which is considered as an unintentionally added compound in conventional plastics and bioplastics (Canellas et al., 2015; Seiko Kato and Conte-junior, 2021), and 2-propenoic acid, 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-, 2-ethylhexyl ester, an organic UV-B filter.

3.2.3. Quantitative analyses of organic chemicals

3.2.3.1. Organic chemicals in bags. The quantitative chemical analyses by ITEX-DHS-GC-MS/MS of PBAT resin, home-compostable, industrial compostable and PE (conventional, oxodegradable, recycled) bags (Tables S3 and S4) targeted over 100 organic chemicals either used as functional additives or unintentionally added to these materials. The results of the volatile organic compounds identified in the bags and organic additives identified in the leachates are discussed in the Suppl. Mat. (see also Figs. S6, S7 and S8). Full names and CAS numbers of the analytes are shown in Table S2.

Additives quantified in compostable bags, and much less abundant or absent in the PE bag, were organophosphate flame retardants (e.g. TCPP, TPhP, TEHP and TCrP) (Fig. 3), and some orthophthalates (e.g. DnBP, DiBP) (Fig. 4). Since these additives were virtually absent from the PBAT resin (ID068) they were most likely added during the compounding phase of the bags manufacturing. In contrast, the PBAT resin already carried significant amounts of the restricted orthophthalate

Table 2

Identification by TD/Py-GC-MS analysis of compounds in PBAT resin, home compostable bags (green shadowed cells), industrial compostable bags (beige shadowed cells), and PE bags (grey shadowed cells). Mass spectra correlations are indicated as percentages (%). ¹Identified by thermal desorption, ²identified by pyrolysis. Chemicals are arranged in three clusters: present in compostable materials only, present in PE materials only and common to both kinds of materials. Note that the majority of chemicals used as additives are in the first cluster, i.e. exclusive of compostable materials. Only compounds identified in at least one of the materials with >85 % correlation are shown.

Compound	CAS number	PBAT	Home compost		Industrial compostable					PE		
		ID068	ID016	ID045	ID015	ID069	ID070	ID072	ID073	ID017	ID018	ID046
Compostable materials only												
Glycerol	56-81-5		97 ¹	92 ¹		93 ¹						
3,6-Dimethyl-1,4-dioxane-2,5-dion (meso form)	4511-42-6				83 ¹ , 98 ²		98 ¹ , 97 ²	99 ²	98 ²			
5-Hydroxymethylfurfural	67-47-0			79 ¹					96 ¹			
2-Furfural	98-01-1								98 ¹ , 99 ²			
2-Hydroxy-6,8-dioxabicyclo[3.2.1]octan-4-one	–		90 ¹	91 ¹	88 ¹							
Levogluconan	498-07-7		99 ¹ , 98 ²	97 ¹ , 98 ²	95 ¹	93 ¹		93 ¹ , 95 ²				
Stearic acid	57-11-4		88 ¹	77 ¹								
Octadecyl 2-ethylhexanoate	59130-70-0	97 ¹										
Fluorene	86-73-7					99 ¹	97 ¹	99 ¹	98 ¹			
Fluorenone	486-25-9					99 ¹	94 ¹					
4-tert-Octylphenol	140-66-9					97 ¹	98 ¹	97 ¹	98 ¹			
Acetoxyacetone	592-20-1						98 ¹					
But-3-enyl 4-hydroxybutyl adipate	–	85 ¹ , 92 ²	85 ¹ , 98 ²	98 ¹ , 97 ²	94 ²	94 ¹ , 91 ²	96 ¹ , 78 ²	95 ¹	89 ¹ , 94 ²			
Diethyl phthalate	117-84-0				99 ¹							
Tetradecanoic acid	544-63-8		96 ¹									
1-Pentadecanol	629-76-5		97 ¹									
Hexadecanenitrile	629-79-8					95 ¹						
Octadecanenitrile	638-65-3		94 ¹			97 ¹						
Eicosanenitrile	–									91 ²		
Butyl isobutyl phthalate	17851-53-5		94 ¹									
Hexadecanamide	629-54-9		98 ¹									
Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	117-81-7	98 ¹	78 ¹									
Eicosanamide	51360-63-5		90 ¹									
1,3-Butadiene	106-99-0	99 ²	99 ²	99 ²	99 ²	87 ²	86 ²	82 ²	78 ²			
Methylglyoxal	78-98-8		97 ²	98 ²	98 ²				93 ²			
Hydroxyacetaldehyde	141-46-8			98 ²	97 ²							
Diethyl ether (mixed with Ethoxyethene)	60-29-7		95 ²									
2,3-Butanedione	431-03-8				64 ²					91 ²		
	- 2											
Crotonaldehyde	4170-30-3		94 ²	85 ²								
Tetrahydrofuran	109-99-9	99 ²	99 ²	99 ²	99 ²	93 ²	90 ²	98 ²	91 ²			
Propionic acid	79-09-4								95 ²			
Acrylic acid	79-10-7						88 ²		95 ²			
4-Vinylcyclohexene	100-40-3								88 ²			
Acetophenone	98-86-2						87 ²					
4-Hydroxybutyl pentanoate	69847-38-7						90 ²		91 ²			
3-Buten-1-ol	627-27-0	99 ²	99 ²	99 ²			99 ²	87 ²	81 ²			
Hydroxyacetone	116-09-6							76 ²	91 ²			
4-Hexanenitrile	628-73-9			86 ²								
Cyclopentanone	120-92-3	97 ²	99 ²	99 ²	99 ²	90 ²	87 ²	99 ²	89 ²			
2-Cyclopentenone	930-30-3	72 ²	93 ²	89 ²	87 ²	84 ²	83 ²	96 ²	91 ²			
Methyl acrylate	96-33-3		84 ²	92 ²	85 ²		81 ²					
3-Butenyl propionate	27819-06-3	99 ²	93 ²	92 ²	98 ²							
Styrene	100-42-5	98 ²	98 ²	94 ²	97 ²	95 ²		96 ²	63 ²			
n-Butanoic acid	107-92-6	93 ²	97 ²									
Hexanoic acid	142-62-1			95 ²	93 ²	91 ²	86 ²	85 ²	92 ²			
5-Methylfuran-2(3H)-one	591-12-8				92 ²							
2-Ethyl-2-hexenal	645-62-5		81 ²		86 ²							
3-Butenyl pentanoate	–	98 ²	97 ²	97 ²	97 ²	96 ²	97 ²	91 ²	97 ²			
Benzoic acid	65-85-0	99 ²	99 ²	98 ²	99 ²	98 ²	90 ¹ , 99 ²	99 ²	98 ²			
4-Methylbenzoic acid	99-94-5	96 ²			96 ²				91 ²			
But-3-enyl benzoate	18203-32-2	99 ²	99 ²	99 ²	99 ²	93 ²	98 ²	99 ²	91 ²			
Biphenyl	92-52-4	97 ²	96 ²	92 ²	68 ²	86 ²	94 ¹ , 98 ²	80 ¹ , 86 ²	83 ¹ , 91 ²			

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Compound	CAS number	PBAT ID068	Home compost		Industrial compostable					PE		
			ID016	ID045	ID015	ID069	ID070	ID072	ID073	ID017	ID018	ID046
Monobut-3-enyl adipate	64084-45-3	96 ²	96 ²	96 ²	96 ²	94 ¹ , 94 ²	93 ^{1,2}	94 ²	94 ²			
Hexamethylene diisocyanate	822-06-0	99 ¹										
1,6-Dioxacyclododecane-7,12-dione	777-95-7	96 ¹	HPLC	95 ² HPLC	HPLC	83 ¹	92 ¹ , 95 ²	92 ¹ , 65 ²	89 ¹ , 87 ²	HPLC		
4-Hydroxybutyl adipic acid monoester	–				90 ²							
1,7-Dioxacyclododecane-2,8-dione	78773-28-1	95 ¹ , 96 ²	95 ²	95 ²	94 ²	71 ²						
Benzophenone	119-61-9		97 ²	95 ²	94 ²		96 ²					
4-Hydroxy-2-methoxybenzophenone	131-57-7							98 ¹				
2-Hydroxyethyl benzoate	94-33-7	98 ²	95 ²	95 ²	94 ²	97 ¹ , 98 ²	83 ¹	97 ¹ , 92 ²	96 ¹			
Dibut-3-enyl adipate	–	98 ²	85 ¹ , 98 ²	98 ²	97 ²	98 ¹ , 87 ²	94 ¹ , 88 ²	92 ¹ , 98 ²	92 ¹ , 87 ²			
But-3-enyl 4-(pentanoyloxy)butyl adipate	–	96 ²	84 ²	96 ²	96 ²	90 ¹	92 ¹	86 ¹	83 ¹			
Erucamide	112-84-5		91 ¹ , 94 ²	95 ^{1, 2}	94 ²	66 ²						
Dibut-3-enyl'-butane-1,4-diyl diterephthalate	–	82 ²					94 ²					
Common to compostable and PE materials												
2-Propenoic acid, 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-, 2-ethylhexyl ester	5466-77-3	90 ¹	92 ¹	91 ¹	90 ¹					95 ¹	93 ¹	97 ¹
Palmitic acid	57-10-3		98 ¹	98 ¹ HPLC	98 ¹ HPLC							81 ¹
1-Tricosene	18835-32-0			86 ¹						89 ¹		89 ¹
Eruconitrile	73170-89-5			96 ¹	97 ¹					95 ¹		95 ¹
Squalene	111-02-4	98 ¹	96 ¹ , 70 ²	97 ¹ , 96 ²	97 ¹					97 ¹	95 ¹	97 ¹
Dibut-3-enyl'-butane-1,4-diyl diadipate	–	95 ²	81 ¹ , 95 ²	92 ¹ , 95 ²	96 ¹ , 95 ²	93 ¹	92 ¹ , 89 ²	93 ²	92 ¹ , 93 ²	95 ¹		
Butane-1,4-diyl dibenzoate	19224-27-2	98 ²	68 ¹ , 74 ²	78 ¹ , 67 ²	96 ²	76 ¹ , 81 ²	72 ¹ , 76 ²	79 ^{1,2}	64 ¹ , 83 ²	74 ¹		
Oleic acid	112-80-1		89 ¹							85	89 ¹	
Oleamide	301-02-0		99 ¹			95 ¹			93 ²	84 ¹		
1,6,13,18-Tetraoxacyclotetracosane-7,12,19,24-tetraone (biodegradable food packaging)	78837-87-3	98 ²	95 ¹ , 89 ²	97 ^{1, 2}	90 ¹ , 98 ²	84 ¹ , 94 ²	95 ¹ , 94 ²	93 ¹	84 ¹ , 96 ²	96 ¹		
4-(Benzoyloxy)butyl but-3-enyl terephthalate	–	87 ²	75 ²	83 ¹ , 77 ²	85 ¹ , 78 ²	72 ¹ , 76 ²	77 ¹ , 78 ²			72 ¹		
Benzene	71-43-2	99 ²	99 ²	99 ²	99 ²	98 ¹ , 94 ²	98 ¹	94 ¹ , 98 ²	95 ¹ , 97 ²	91 ²		91 ²
Toluene	108-88-3	99 ²	99 ²	99 ²	96 ²	96 ²	84 ²	75 ²	95 ²	76 ²		76 ²
Di(but-3-enyl) terephthalate	62680-75-5	98 ^{1,2}	80 ¹ , 98 ²	66 ¹ , 98 ²	68 ¹ , 94 ²	96 ¹ , 82 ²	97 ¹ , 81 ²	93 ¹ , 95 ²	82 ¹ , 91 ²	78 ¹		78 ¹
Dodecanal	112-54-9	87 ¹									97 ¹	81 ¹
Octadecanal	638-66-4	85 ¹								92 ¹	98 ¹	97 ¹
PE materials only												
Octanal	124-13-0										92 ¹	
Nonanal	124-19-6										93 ¹	76 ¹
Tributylene glycol dibutyl ether	143-22-6										93 ¹	
Tridecanal	10486-19-8										83 ¹	98 ¹
4,8-Dimethyl-1-tridecene	–										87 ¹	
Hexadecanal	629-80-1											94 ¹
1-Octadecanol	112-92-5										93 ¹	98 ¹
Propylene (mixed with propane)	115-07-1									97 ²		99 ²
1-Butene	106-98-9									92 ²	83 ²	95 ²
1-Pentene	109-67-1									97 ²		97 ²
Cyclopentene	142-29-0									83 ²		90 ²
1-Hexene	592-41-6									99 ²	86 ²	99 ²
Methylcyclopentane	96-37-7									87 ²		
2,4-Hexadiene	592-46-1									95 ²		83 ²
1,3-Hexadiene	592-48-3									96 ²		
Cyclohexene	110-83-8									96 ²		96 ²
1-Heptene	592-76-7									99 ²	70 ²	99 ²
n-Heptane	142-82-5									98 ²		98 ²
2,4-Dimethyl-1-heptene	19549-87-2											97 ²
2-Methyl-1-nonene	2980-71-4											95 ²

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Compound	CAS number	PBAT ID068	Home compost		Industrial compostable					PE		
			ID016	ID045	ID015	ID069	ID070	ID072	ID073	ID017	ID018	ID046
n-alkanes 8 to 40C	–									>90 ²	>90 ²	>90 ²
Alkenes 8 to 40C	–									>90 ²	>90 ²	>90 ²
Alkadienes 8 to 40C	–									>90 ²	>90 ²	>90 ²

Fig. 3. Concentration of organophosphate flame-retardants (OPFR) ($\mu\text{g/g}$) measured by ITEX-DHS-GC-MS/MS in a conventional PE bag (ID017) vs PBAT resin (ID068) and seven PBAT-based compostable plastic bags. Note the resin lacks OPFRs and the conventional single-use PE bag shows much lower levels than all compostable bags.

Fig. 4. Concentration of orthophthalates ($\mu\text{g/g}$) measured by ITEX-DHS-GC-MS/MS in a conventional PE bag (ID017) vs PBAT resin (ID068) and seven PBAT-based compostable plastic bags. Note the conventional single-use PE bag shows the lowest levels of phthalates.

DnOP (see Table S3). There is solid evidence that TPhP is an estrogenic EDC, and TCrP is an antagonist of the androgenic receptor (Bajard et al., 2021). TCPP showed some evidence of estrogenic effects on sea-urchins within the $\mu\text{g/L}$ range (Campoy-López et al., 2020). In addition, TPhP is a toxic substance with category 1 aquatic acute and chronic toxicity according to ECHA. Concerning the orthophthalates DnBP and DiBP, both are categorized by ECHA as endocrine disruptors, designated as having the potential to cause short and long-term aquatic toxicity and are currently undergoing assessment for PBT classification. DCHP, only quantified in ID070, is also classified as endocrine disruptor and as to cause long term aquatic toxicity by ECHA. The phthalate-substitute plasticizer ATBC was the most abundant additive in bag ID045. In addition, concentration of the potential endocrine disruptor BPA was higher in this bag than in others.

The total amount of orthophthalates in the compostable bags is remarkably higher than in the PE bags (Fig. 4), especially if we focus on the suspected endocrine disruptors with ester chains between 4 and 8C (DiBP, DEHP, DnBP and DCHP). Using a different analytical method,

Moreno Abril et al. (2024) reported even higher amounts of DEHP in compostable bags ($49 \mu\text{g/g}$), recycled PE bags ($40 \mu\text{g/g}$) and PE bags ($16 \mu\text{g/g}$).

The mechanical properties of PE are more favourable than those of alternative biopolymers in order to produce thin films by extrusion, and this contributes to explaining its lower levels of plasticizers (Tyagi and Bhattacharya, 2019). However, the largest difference in composition in terms of functional additives concerns organophosphate flame-retardants, largely more abundant in all compostable bags compared to single-use PE bag (Fig. 3). Note that these chemicals are added during the compounding phase of the bags manufacturing, since the PBAT resin lacks any OPFR. Because of these differences between PE and compostable polymers, the overall content of chemical additives classified by ECHA as toxic to reproduction and/or endocrine disruptors is remarkably higher in all compostable bags compared to both the virgin PBAT (ID068) and the conventional PE bags (ID017).

Although minority in concentration, it is worth pointing at the presence of 2,6-DIPN, compound used in the synthesis of monomers, in

the PBAT resin (see Table S3). This chemical is classified by ECHA as very toxic to aquatic life with long lasting effects.

Chemicals common to all bags according to this analysis included antioxidant BHT, light protectant benzophenone, and some adipate and phthalate plasticizers, including the restricted DEHP. Finally, additives exclusive of the PE bag, absent or much less abundant in the compostable bags, include antioxidants TBHQ and Ionox100. The composition of antioxidants and light stabilizers is much more brand-dependent than that of plasticizers and OPFRs (Fig. 6), and we cannot rule out the possibility that other chemicals with this function were present but not identified in this targeted analysis. Most likely, ID069 carries some stabilizer not targeted in this analysis.

3.2.4. Analysis of metals

3.2.4.1. Metals in bags. The metal contents found in the compostable bags (Table 3 and Fig. S9) is in compliance with the limits regulated for packaging recoverable through composting and biodegradation (CEN, 2000) and for treatment in well-managed home composting installations (CEN, 2022), except for ID016 (home-compostable bag) whose Cu content exceeds the limit of 50 µg/g. PE bags are obviously not intended for composting, but they also show metal values below the limits, except for Cu and Zn (limit 150 µg/g) in the recycled bag (ID046), and Zn in the oxodegradable bag (ID018). This bag (ID018) in fact shows the maximum level of Cd and Zn among all materials tested.

Co, Hg, Sb were not detected in any of the bags, while Cr and Fe were the only elements detected in all the bags and generally in low concentrations except for Fe in ID046 (recycled bag).

The values found in PE bags are similar or even lower to those previously reported for different types of PE bags (Alam et al., 2019, 2018; Huerta-Pujol et al., 2010). The recycled PE bag (ID046) is the bag showing more metals above detection level, and also a remarkably higher content of Cu and Fe compared to any other bag. Lowe et al. (2021) characterized previously several recycled products, including food packaging and other plastic objects, and also demonstrated the higher amount of additives found on them comparing to first-use materials. The oxodegradable PE bag (ID018), in turn, shows the highest Zn content. Regarding compostable bags, ID045 and 072 are the bags in

which the lowest number of metals have been quantified and in the lowest concentrations whereas ID016 and ID070 show the highest values. Nevertheless, the concentrations are similar to those found in the literature for compostable bags (Huerta-Pujol et al., 2010).

Except for ID045, all other bags show Ca or Ba as the most abundant metals. Calcium carbonate (also identified in the FTIR spectra of several materials) and Barium sulphate are common fillers added in the manufacturing process of the bags, helping them in the extrusion process and improving mechanical properties such as impact strength, tearing or punching resistance in the final product (Shahzamani et al., 2012; Ippolito et al., 2021).

Also, the high levels of chromium quantified in the PBAT resin are remarkable, which is frequently used as a polymerization aid for olefins (McDaniel, 2010).

3.2.4.2. Metals in bag leachates. The values found in the leachates of the bags studied are very similar (Table 4). No remarkable differences were found between conventional PE and compostable bags. The most abundant metals in the bags, Ca and Mg, are also predominant in the leachate. The high values for Ca and Mg are also likely due to the presence of these ions in the seawater used to prepare the leachates.

3.3. Ecotoxicity

3.3.1. Compostable vs PE bags

Very clear differences in toxicity to invertebrate models, copepod larvae, sea-urchin embryos and mussel embryos, among compostable vs PE bags were identified (Tables 5 and 6). Leachates of all compostable bags tested showed relevant toxicity in the SET and mussel embryo tests, and three of them were toxic to copepods, whereas none of the PE bags were toxic to any test species except for the slight toxicity of ID018 on mussel embryos. This was consistent with the lack of toxicity of the PE resin vs the moderate toxicity of the PBAT resin in both invertebrate species tested. None of the leachates tested were toxic for microalgae, although this test, due to the need of diluting the leachate before testing, was the least sensitive.

Therefore, the current experimental results reveal a consistent pattern of higher toxicity in PBAT-based compared to PE-based plastic

Table 3

Metal concentrations (µg/g) measured by ICP-MS in plastic bags ($n = 3$). The higher values for each metal are marked in bold. n.a. not analysed.

µg/g	PBAT	Home comp		Industrial compostable					PE		
	ID068	ID016	ID045	ID072	ID015	ID069	ID070	ID073	ID017	ID018	ID046
As	n.a.	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	0.14 ± 0.001	<0.06	<0.06	0.13 ± 0.04	0.17 ± 0.01
Ba	n.a.	5745 ± 70.5	<0.13	<0.13	0.28 ± 0.001	7248 ± 222	1.61 ± 0.06	1.05 ± 0.003	2.40 ± 0.08	425 ± 6.94	30.3 ± 0.30
Ca	n.a.	467 ± 4.03	<5.00	25.9 ± 10.7	19,786 ± 270	2720 ± 32.6	51,990 ± 582	29,750 ± 342	9538 ± 64.1	58,711 ± 1021	16,118 ± 357
Cd	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	0.16 ± 0.004	<0.06
Co	<0.56	<0.56	<0.56	<0.56	<0.56	<0.56	<0.56	<0.56	<0.56	<0.56	<0.56
Cr	5.68 ± 1.06	4.98 ± 0.18	0.26 ± 0.01	0.36 ± 0.03	0.29 ± 0.01	1.42 ± 0.01	0.76 ± 0.07	0.38 ± 0.16	1.14 ± 0.01	1.81 ± 0.10	3.57 ± 0.28
Cu	0.55 ± 0.01	64.4 ± 2.68	11.4 ± 1.06	<0.13	3.12 ± 0.03	35.8 ± 0.68	8.49 ± 0.37	4.70 ± 1.26	<0.13	18.6 ± 0.85	442 ± 9.31
Fe	42.8 ± 13.0	34.2 ± 0.46	99.2 ± 4.93	10.4 ± 2.50	11.0 ± 0.58	29.9 ± 5.75	424 ± 16.1	15.2 ± 0.64	22.7 ± 2.73	28.1 ± 6.55	3549 ± 35.3
Hg	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Mg	n.a.	1604 ± 11.5	14.4 ± 0.13	9.53 ± 0.44	143 ± 1.44	379 ± 3.62	3150 ± 608	55.7 ± 2.52	48.3 ± 1.01	205 ± 1.98	169 ± 5.73
Mn	<0.63	<0.63	<0.63	<0.63	<0.63	<0.63	5.17 ± 0.06	2.67 ± 0.02	1.62 ± 0.05	<0.63	3.77 ± 0.07
Pb	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	0.27 ± 0.02	0.25 ± 0.05	<0.06	1.43 ± 0.12	0.48 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.03
Sb	<1.25	<1.25	<1.25	<1.25	<1.25	<1.25	<1.25	<1.25	<1.25	<1.25	<1.25
Sn	0.13 ± 0.01	<0.06	<0.06	3.07 ± 0.03	2.04 ± 0.04	<0.06	3.12 ± 0.02	0.78 ± 0.09	0.22 ± 0.02	<0.06	0.17 ± 0.01
Zn	n.a.	8.06 ± 2.23	7.00 ± 0.10	<1.25	<1.25	44.4 ± 0.06	143 ± 12.7	<1.25	111 ± 2.24	471 ± 21.8	251 ± 3.94

Table 4

Metal concentrations ($\mu\text{g/L}$) measured by ICP-MS in bag leachates ($n = 3$). The highest values for each metal are marked in bold. High Ca and Mg levels are expected considering their background concentration in seawater.

$\mu\text{g/L}$	Home compostable		Ind compostable	PE
	ID016	ID045	ID015	ID017
Al	236 ± 3.42	30.4 ± 0.33	<25.0	218 ± 5.99
As	<0.50	<0.50	0.72 ± 0.10	<0.50
Ba	49.4 ± 0.40	39.5 ± 0.47	33.2 ± 0.09	30.6 ± 0.33
Be	<2.50	<2.50	<2.50	<2.50
Ca	402,609 ± 5018	355,774 ± 4413	417,051 ± 4996	400,853 ± 5018
Cd	<2.50	<2.50	<2.50	<2.50
Co	<2.50	<2.50	<2.50	<2.50
Cr	<5.00	<5.00	<5.00	<5.00
Cu	<2.50	<2.50	<2.50	<2.50
Fe	14.0 ± 0.23	23.7 ± 0.15	<10.0	<10.0
Hg	<0.50	<0.50	<0.50	<0.50
Mg	1,167,534 ± 7287	1,153,908 ± 20,637	1,195,377 ± 8952	1,150,130 ± 12,018
Mn	<25.0	<25.0	<25.0	<25.0
Mo	1.60 ± 0.06	1.40 ± 0.08	1.29 ± 0.19	1.41 ± 0.08
Ni	<25.0	<25.0	<25.0	<25.0
Pb	<1.25	1.85 ± 0.02	<1.25	<1.25
Sb	<0.50	<0.50	<0.50	<0.50
Se	23.7 ± 2.41	31.0 ± 2.01	29.0 ± 2.44	28.7 ± 4.41
Sn	<2.50	<2.50	<2.50	<2.50
Sr	7793 ± 100	7582 ± 89.0	7969 ± 106	7583 ± 46.0
Ti	7.20 ± 0.20	4.55 ± 0.17	<1.25	2.99 ± 0.07
V	<0.50	<0.50	<0.50	<0.50
Zn	<25.0	485 ± 1.63	33.3 ± 0.59	<25.0

bags that will be discussed below.

When comparing the sensitivity of the different test species, we find that organisms showing unprotected early life stages (sea-urchin and bivalve embryos with naked cell membranes directly in contact with the surrounding medium) are remarkably more sensitive than fish embryos, protected by the egg chorion, and microalgal cells, protected by the cell wall. The chitin exoskeleton of copepod nauplii seems to provide an

intermediate level of protection. Variability among taxa in detoxification metabolism and biochemical routes targeted by the potential toxicants are likely to further contribute to the differences in sensitivity here reported.

Recently, focus of plastic environmental research has shifted to the potential toxic effects of chemicals used to manufacture plastic materials (Gunaalan et al., 2020), especially for those presented as ecologically friendly alternatives (Laranjeiro et al., 2024). In vitro toxicity tests challenge the preconception that potentially biodegradable plastics and plant-based materials are chemically safer than conventional plastics (Klein et al., 2021b; Wang et al., 2023; Zimmermann et al., 2020, 2019). More recently, Moreno Abril et al. (2024) studied the effects on biotransformation and endocrine disruption biomarkers in fish caused by leachates of conventional and alternative plastic bags, and concluded that “eco-friendly” bags are not less harmful to fish, in terms of gene expression alterations, than conventional PE.

In vitro tests commonly use extracts obtained with organic solvents. Previous studies from our group using in vivo tests and seawater leachates support this view, since potentially biodegradable polymers

Table 6

Assessment criteria for the classification of the marine ecotoxicity of leachates obtained from plastic materials applicable to the microalgal and invertebrate toxicity tests.

microalgae		invertebrates	
TU	Toxicity	TU	Toxicity
		< 1	None
<2	None or Slight	1 ≤ TU < 2	Slight
2 ≤ TU < 5	Relevant	2 ≤ TU < 5	Relevant
≥ 5	High	≥ 5	High

Table 5

Toxicity of the leachates obtained at 1 g plastic per litre of seawater in each marine bioassay. TU: toxic units. Color scale explained in Table 6. In algal tests minimum dilution is 1/2 and thus minimum toxicity is <2 TU. n.t. not tested. *10 g/L leachate.

ID	Description	Microalga	Acartia	SET	Mussel	Fish
		1 g/L	1 g/L	1 g/L	10 g/L	10 g/L
PE materials						
ID148	LDPE resin	< 2 TU	< 1 TU	< 1 TU	n.t.	n.t.
ID017	Conventional PE carrier bag (10 L)	< 2 TU	< 1 TU	< 1 TU	< 1 TU	< 1 TU
ID018	Oxodegradable carrier bag (10 L)	< 2 TU	< 1 TU	< 1 TU	3.08 TU	< 1 TU
ID046	Recycled PE trash sac (30 L)	< 2 TU	< 1 TU	< 1 TU	< 1 TU	< 1 TU
PBAT materials						
ID068	PBAT resin pellets	< 2 TU	1.68 TU	1.59 TU	n.t.	n.t.
ID016	Home compostable bag (6 L)	< 2 TU	1.72 TU	3.65 TU	11.0 TU	< 1 TU
ID045	Home compostable trash sac (30 L)	< 2 TU	2.20 TU	2.41 TU	9.84 TU	< 1 TU
ID015	Industrial compostable carrier bag (6 L)	< 2 TU	< 1 TU	2.37 TU	9.77	< 1 TU
ID069	Industrial compostable trash sac (6 L)	<1.5 TU*	< 1 TU	2.67 TU	7.74 TU	n.t.
ID070	Industrial compostable can liner (50 L)	<1.5 TU*	1.55 TU	3.0 TU	6.89 TU	< 1 TU
ID072	Compostable trash sac (10 L)	< 2 TU	< 1 TU	5.24 TU	5.74	< 1 TU

(Uribe-Echeverría and Beiras, 2022; Laranjeiro et al., 2024) and compostable bags (Quade et al., 2023, 2022) showed higher in vivo aquatic toxicity than their conventional PE counterparts. Moreover, environmental degradation may increase ecotoxicity of compostable materials whereas PE bags remain unaffected (Quade et al., 2023; López-Ibáñez et al., under review).

It is important to note that none of the above-mentioned studies are intended for human health or environmental risk assessment. Lack of environmental relevance of toxicity tests conducted with organic solvents can be illustrated with the results from Klein et al. (Klein et al., 2021b), who found 100 % mortality in *Lumbriculus variegatus* worms exposed to methanolic extracts of microplastics whereas aqueous leachates of those microplastics had almost no adverse effects on the worms. Taylor et al. (1994) found that PLA toxicity in microtox tests was a result of the low pH conditions and disappeared when a buffer was added to the experimental medium. The present study used seawater extracts in order to increase ecological relevance of the results. Still, concentrations tested are not ecologically relevant. The actual relevance of these laboratory studies is to stress the need of avoiding the use of potentially toxic chemicals in the unknown composition of plastic materials and conduct a priori assessments of the chemicals added to plastics to warrant chemical safety of commercial materials intended to be common household items.

The present study presents further experimental evidence pointing at a higher potential toxicity for aquatic organisms of compostable plastics compared to new, conventional, recycled and oxodegradable polyethylene. Manufacturing thin films using biopolymers is technically more challenging than using PE. PLA for example is particularly brittle and sticky, and demands specific impact-modifiers, slip and antiblock chemicals (Markarian, 2008). Biocides are the plastic additives posing most chemical hazards, considering their toxicity to mammals, ecotoxicity, environmental fate, and physicochemical properties (Barrick et al., 2021). Uribe-Echeverría and Beiras (2022) identified in the biodegradable polymer PHB non-volatile chlorinated, brominated and iodinated hydrocarbons likely used as microbiocides, not present in conventional plastics, and Laranjeiro et al. (2024) detected 2,4,6-trichlorophenol in leachates from another biodegradable polyhydroxyalkanoate, the PHBv. None of those chemicals were identified in the analyses here conducted. However, we detected in the PBAT resin and in one of the compostable

bags a synthetic pesticide used as sprout inhibitor for stored potatoes, 2,6-DIPN.

ITEX-DHS-GC-MS/MS analyses quantified remarkably higher concentrations of orthophthalates and OPFRs in compostable bags compared to conventional PE bags (see Figs. 4 and 5). This is alarming considering that some of these chemicals are restricted in many applications because they are suspected of endocrine disruption in vertebrates. However, these highly insoluble chemicals showed low short term toxicity to invertebrate larvae (for OPFRs see Beiras (2021)); for phthalates see (Beiras et al., 2021; Passino and Smith, 1987), and thus cannot be invoked in order to explain the higher toxicity of the compostable bag leachates.

Quade et al. (2023) found higher UV absorbance in compostable bags compared to PE materials, as expected from lack of aromatic radicals in the latter and associated increased toxicity in the compostable materials upon UV light exposure. Whereas this might play a role in the toxicity found in the copepod tests, both SET and mussel embryo tests are conducted in the dark, and thus the toxicity of the lixivates observed in those tests cannot be due to those photo-oxidation processes.

3.3.2. Effect of bacteria on toxicity

Degradation of compostable materials promotes heterotrophic bacteria and other microorganisms. The home-compostable bag ID016 (see Table 1) was used to test the hypothesis that this microbial flora might explain the higher toxicity of compostable bags on sea-urchin embryos. The standard leachate of these bags was tested in parallel with a leachate from the same material obtained in sterile conditions with a further 0.22 μm filtration. The 0.22 μm filter successfully reduced the bacterial density in the leachates compared to standard methods. After filtration, no CFU were observed neither in the control with ASW nor in both leachates. On the contrary, after 48 h incubation at 20 °C, 5500 CFU mL^{-1} were counted in the case of the standard filtering process versus only 200 CFU mL^{-1} in the case of the 0.22- μm filtered one. The ASW control remained sterile, and no colonies were found. Independently of the CFU growth found, both types of leachates tested showed the same toxicity: 2.2 TUs. Hence, these findings lead to the conclusion that microbial growth takes place during the SET incubation when lixivates from compostable bags are present, probably due to the presence of degradable compounds such as starch, but this microbial growth does

Fig. 5. Concentration of chemical additives considered by ECHA as toxic to reproduction, endocrine disrupters or both in a conventional PE bag (ID017) vs PBAT resin (ID068) and seven PBAT-based compostable plastic bags.

Fig. 6. Concentration of antioxidants and light stabilizers ($\mu\text{g/g}$) measured by ITEX-DHS-GC-MS/MS in a conventional PE bag (ID017) vs PBAT resin (ID068) and seven PBAT-based compostable plastic bags. Note that the PBAT resin shows low levels of BHT, although most likely items 068 and 069 carry some stabilizer not targeted in these analyses.

not affect the toxicity results.

4. Conclusions

- In terms of major components, the composition of commercial compostable bags currently present in the market was surprisingly homogeneous. The major component in the seven brands analysed was the same, PBAT. Four of the seven brands are actually heteropolymers that combine PBAT with PLA, a biobased material with complementary mechanical properties to oil-based PBAT. Finally, six of the seven brands showed in addition starch, the only exception was the largest bag (ID070), advertised as especially tough in terms of mechanical resistance.

- Given the numerous and heterogeneous substances used by the plastic industry, and the complex composition of a polymeric material, the chemical profile of a plastic item cannot be described by using a single analytical method. Therefore, a combination of advanced analytical techniques such as spectrometry (FTIR, ICP), chromatography (GC) and mass spectrometry (MS), along with green microextraction techniques (ITEX-DHS and SPME Arrow) and thermal analysis (TD and Py), were used to provide a comprehensive chemical characterization of over 130 organic additives and monomers and 23 metals in commercial plastic bags and their leachates.

- Compostable plastic items show a particularly complex chemical composition, and when n-alkanes and alkenes are excluded, non-target analytical methods reveal a higher number of organic molecules in these materials compared to PE materials. When plastic additives are specifically targeted, the number of chemicals and concentrations are generally higher in compostable bags than in the PE counterparts (conventional, oxodegradable and recycled PE). Among additives remarkably more abundant in compostable than in PE bags there are chemicals registered in the EU as toxic in aquatic environments at level 1 (BHT, DiBP) and 2 (BP, DnBP, DCHP).

- Recycled PE bags show much higher Cu and Zn levels than single use PE and compostable bags. However, no differences in short term aquatic toxicity were found between recycled and single use PE materials.

- Although the sensitivity of different test species greatly varies, compostable plastic items and PBAT resin consistently show a higher short term aquatic toxicity to marine invertebrates compared to conventional, recycled and oxodegradable PE items. In those cases where leachates showed toxicity, this disappears at dilutions orders of magnitude lower than those expected in natural waters. Therefore, concerning ecological effects at environmentally relevant plastic densities are not expected for any of the materials tested.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

R. Beiras: Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **E. Concha-Graña:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **F.M.G. Laranjeiro:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **V. Fernández-González:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **S. López-Ibáñez:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **C. Moscoso-Pérez:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **A. Vilas:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **S. Muniategui-Lorenzo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.180116>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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